

Statistical Analysis of Composite Fatigue Life

W. J. Park¹⁾, R. Y. Kim²⁾

- 1) Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Wright State University, Dayton, Ohio 45435, U.S.A.
- 2) University of Dayton, 300 College Park Avenue, Dayton, Ohio 45469, U.S.A.

ABSTRACT

A statistical procedure is presented to characterize the S-N fatigue curve of composite laminates with some degree of statistical reliability and to test the residual strength degradation models in composite materials.

A maximum likelihood estimation and pooling techniques are employed to analyze fatigue life data under various fatigue stress levels. The validation of existing residual strength degradation model for composite laminates, under the assumption that the static strength has Weibull distribution, is examined by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov goodness of fit test.

INTRODUCTION

In this paper statistical techniques have been presented to characterize a fatigue S-N curve and to examine the validity of presently used residual strength degradation model for composite materials. Examples are given using tension-tension fatigue data obtained for T300/5208 graphite/epoxy specimens with a $[0/09/+45]_s$ orientation.

The classical S-N curve yields an estimate of the mean time-to-failure (fatigue life) as a function of maximum stress level, but such a procedure fails to account for the large variation in the fatigue life at a given stress level. In this paper a procedure which allows the generation of S-N curves with some statistical value without resorting to an extremely large data base is presented in detail.

The existing residual strength degradation model is presented and estimation of parameters in the model was discussed. The fatigue life under various stress levels, which has two-parameter Weibull distribution, was estimated by maximum likelihood method. Examples and illustrations in the Weibull parameter estimations and the parameter estimations of the residual strength degradation model were given for the composite material T300/5208, Graphite/Epoxy, $[0/90/+45]_s$.

RESIDUAL STRENGTH DEGRADATION MODEL

The residual strength degradation model was used previously to investigate the fatigue behaviors of composite materials by Hahn and Kim (1) and Yang and Liu (2). Experimental fatigue tests of composite materials were conducted commonly under various stress levels S_1, S_2, \dots, S_m of fatigue loading. For each stress level S , the residual strength $X(n)$ after n fatigue cycles should satisfy the following equation (References (1) and (2))

$$X(n)^c = X(0)^c - f(S) \cdot n, \tag{1}$$

where $f(S)$ is a function of the stress level S , c is a constant and $X(0)$ is the ultimate static strength.

The distribution of $X(0)$ is assumed to have a two parameter Weibull distribution,

$$R_o(x) = P_r \left\{ X(0) \geq x \right\} = \exp \left[- \left(\frac{x}{\beta_o} \right)^{\alpha_o} \right], \tag{2}$$

in which α_o is the shape parameter and β_o is the scale parameter or the characteristic strength. The distribution of $X(n)$ can be obtained from equations (1) and (2) as follows:

$$R_n(x) = P_r \left\{ X(n) \geq x \right\} = \exp \left[- \left\{ \left(\frac{x}{\beta_o} \right)^c + \frac{n}{\beta_o^c / f(S)} \right\}^{\alpha_o/c} \right] \tag{3}$$

Let N denote the number of cycles at which fatigue failure occurs under the applied stress level S . Then at the moment of fatigue fracture a relationship, " $X(n) = S$ if and only if $N = n$ " holds and the distribution of fatigue life N can be obtained from Equations (1) and (2) as

$$R_N(n) = P_r \left\{ N \geq n \right\} = \exp. \left[- \left\{ \frac{n + (S^c / f(S))}{\beta_o^c / f(S)} \right\}^{\alpha_o/c} \right]. \tag{4}$$

In general, stress level is low such that $(S / \beta_o)^c < < 1$ Equation (4) is reduced to

$$R_N(n) = \exp. \left[- \left\{ \frac{n}{\beta_o^c / f(S)} \right\}^{\alpha_o/c} \right]. \tag{5}$$

It is noted that the fatigue life N has a two-parameter Weibull distribution with the characteristic life $\beta_o^c / f(S)$ and the shape parameter α_o / c , which is independent of the stress level S .

From a classical $S - N$ curve relationship $K S^b N = 1$, an expression for $f(S)$ is obtained as $f(S) = \beta_o^c K S^b$ since the characteristic life is $N = 1 / K S^b$, $\beta_o^c / f(S)$.

Note that Equation (1), (4) and (5) can be expressed as

$$X(n)^c = X(o)^c - \beta_o^c K S^b n \tag{6}$$

$$R_n(x) = \exp. \left[- \left\{ \left(\frac{x}{\beta_o} \right)^c + \frac{n}{1 / K S^b} \right\}^{\alpha_o/c} \right] \tag{7}$$

and

$$R_N(n) = \exp. \left[- \left(\frac{n}{1 / K S^b} \right)^{\alpha_o/c} \right] \tag{8}$$

POOLED ESTIMATION OF WEIBULL PARAMETERS

Let $x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{in}$ be the fatigue data (under stress level S_i) from the underlying two-parameter Weibull distribution.

$$R_{N_i}(n) = \exp \left[- \left(\frac{n}{\beta_i} \right)^\alpha \right], \quad n > 0, \quad i, 2, \dots, m$$

with a common shape parameter $\alpha = \alpha_0/c$ and scale parameters $\beta_i = 1/K S_i^b$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. The unknown parameters α and β_i can be estimated by the maximum likelihood method: The maximum likelihood equation for estimating α is

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \left[\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} \hat{\alpha} \ln x_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} \hat{\alpha}} - \frac{m}{\hat{\alpha}} - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \ln x_{ij}}{n} \right] = 0 \quad (9)$$

and the corresponding maximum likelihood estimator $\hat{\beta}_i$ of β_i is obtained by

$$\hat{\beta}_i = \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} \hat{\alpha} \right]^{1/\hat{\alpha}} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m. \quad (10)$$

Thomas, Bain and Antle (3) and Cohen (4) have discussed the maximum likelihood estimation in the Weibull distribution for the case $m = 1$.

The results in Table 1 and 2, which were taken from Park (5) can be used to construct confidence intervals for α . The 100 (1- γ) % confidence interval for α will be of the form $(\hat{\alpha}/l_\gamma, \infty)$ where l_γ is obtained from Table 1 such that $P_r(\hat{\alpha}/\alpha \leq l_\gamma) = 1-\gamma$. The 100(1- γ) % confidence interval for β can be constructed and are of the form $(\hat{\alpha} e^{-l_\gamma^*/\hat{\alpha}}, \infty)$ where l_γ^* is obtained from Table 2 such that $P_r(\hat{\alpha} \ln(\beta/\hat{\alpha}) \leq l_\gamma^*) = 1-\gamma$.

TABLE 1
PERCENTAGE POINTS, l_γ , SUCH THAT $P_r(\hat{\alpha}/\alpha < l_\gamma) = 1-\gamma$

m	n		5	6	7	8	9	10
	1- γ							
3	.90		1.642	1.534	1.457	1.391	1.360	1.329
	.95		1.811	1.677	1.569	1.497	1.450	1.406
	.98		2.049	1.852	1.723	1.620	1.561	1.515
4	.90		1.554	1.457	1.393	1.343	1.313	1.288
	.95		1.704	1.557	1.490	1.430	1.388	1.357
	.98		1.872	1.704	1.610	1.530	1.480	1.442
5	.90		1.505	1.412	1.353	1.313	1.280	1.258
	.95		1.620	1.502	1.438	1.385	1.348	1.321
	.98		1.763	1.625	1.536	1.480	1.430	1.399

TABLE 2
 PERCENTAGE POINTS, ℓ_{γ}^* , SUCH THAT $P_r (\hat{\alpha} \ln(\hat{\beta}/\beta) < \ell_{\gamma}^*) = 1-\gamma$

m	1- γ	n					
		5	6	7	8	9	10
3	.90	0.655	0.578	0.533	0.488	0.453	0.420
3	.95	0.875	0.768	0.701	0.639	0.589	0.548
3	.98	1.116	0.997	0.905	0.816	0.751	0.710
4	.90	0.656	0.571	0.521	0.480	0.445	0.422
4	.95	0.849	0.746	0.679	0.628	0.581	0.555
4	.98	1.094	0.955	0.858	0.781	0.736	0.700
5	.90	0.648	0.570	0.513	0.466	0.436	0.416
5	.95	0.836	0.737	0.660	0.606	0.569	0.537
5	.98	1.063	0.940	0.845	0.764	0.710	0.671

S-N CURVE CHARACTERIZATION

From the characteristic life $\hat{\beta}_i = 1/KS_i^b$, by taking natural logarithm transform, we can obtain

$$\ln \hat{\beta}_i = -b \cdot \ln S_i - \ln K. \tag{11}$$

The parameters b and K can be estimated by taking a linear least square fit on Equation (11). We can also estimate the value of c by solving $\hat{\alpha} = \hat{\alpha}_0/c$.

The 95% confidence interval (one-sided) for β_i can be obtained from Table 2 as follows:

$$P_r \left\{ \hat{\alpha} \ln (\hat{\beta}_i/\beta_i) \leq \ell^*_{.05} \right\} = .95 \quad \text{i.e.}$$

$$P_r \left\{ \hat{\beta}_i \exp \left[- (\ell^*_{.05}/\hat{\alpha}) \right] \leq \beta_i \right\} = .95$$

Let us denote the lower bound of 95% confidence interval for β_i by $\underline{\beta}_i$, then $\underline{\beta}_i$ is given by

$$\underline{\beta}_i = \hat{\beta}_i \exp \left[- (\ell^*_{.05}/\hat{\alpha}) \right]. \tag{12}$$

A-allowable (or B-allowable) as a material fatigue design value is defined by the probabilistic statement that we can be 95% confident of the assertion that the probability of surviving the A-allowable value is at least 0.99 (or 0.90 for B-allowable) (See Lemon and Wattier (6)). Therefore, A-allowable x_{Ai} under the stress level S_i , $i=1,2,\dots,m$, can be obtained by solving the following equation;

$$R(x_{Ai}) = \exp \left[- \left(\frac{x_{Ai}}{\underline{\beta}_i} \right)^{\hat{\alpha}} \right] = 0.99 ; \tag{13}$$

where $\underline{\beta}_i$ is the 95% confidence lower limit for β_i . That is

$$x_{Ai} = \underline{\beta}_i \left[- \ln (.99) \right]^{1/\hat{\alpha}}. \tag{14}$$

From equations (11), (12) and (14), we have obtained

$$\ln \underline{\beta}_i = - b \ln S_i - \ln K - (\ell^*_{.05}/\hat{\alpha}), \tag{15}$$

and

$$\ln x_{Ai} = -b \ln S_i - \ln K - (\ell^* / \hat{\alpha}) + \frac{1}{\hat{\alpha}} \ln \left[-\ln(.99) \right] \quad (16)$$

which are the S-N fatigue curve equations where N_i is represented by β_i and x_{Ai} respectively. We note that the slopes of straight line in Equations (11), (12) and (14) are the same value $-b$, which is due to the fact that the shape parameter α is independent of the applied stress level S_i .

EXAMPLE DATA

The S-N curve characterization technique and goodness of fit test (see Gibbons (7)) for the residual strength degradation model were applied to data obtained from fatigue tests for T300/5208 graphite/epoxy specimens which had a [0/90/+45] orientation. The specimen geometry is straight sided coupon with 1.9 cm (.75") wide and 12.7 cm (5") long in gage section. The specimens were fatigue cycled under tension-tension load with the stress ratio 0.1 at 10 Hz. Five replicas at five stress levels were obtained and data points were listed in Table 3.

TABLE 3
FATIGUE DATA T300/5208
G/E [0/90/+45]_s

Stress Level MPa	Fatigue Failure Cycle (10 Hz)				
483	1,150	1,850	2,436	3,768	6,898
448	2,620	4,920	6,490	7,000	9,020
414	10,300	21,270	22,550	28,760	78,720
375	71,050	108,550	168,700	169,480	325,780
345	412,000	614,960	764,680	1,333,390	1,367,890

The pooled estimate $\hat{\alpha}$ of the common shape parameter α is obtained from Equation (9) and is given by $\hat{\alpha} = 1.95$. The estimates β_i of the characteristic life β_i are computed using Equation (10) and the values are listed in Table 4.

TABLE 4
MAXIMUM LIKELIHOOD ESTIMATES OF β_i FOR
FATIGUE DATA, T300/5208 G/E [0/90/+45]_s

Stress Level S_i (MPa)	$\ln S_i$	$\hat{\beta}_i$	$\ln \hat{\beta}_i$
483	6.180	3,779	8.239
448	6.105	6,364	8.758
414	6.026	39,834	10.592
379	5.938	188,780	12.148
345	5.846	974,263	13.789

The Weibull parameters of static strength were estimated from 29 data points and are given by

$$\hat{\alpha}_0 = 18.0 \text{ and } \hat{\beta} = 598.4 \text{ MPa.}$$

The coefficient c in the residual strength degradation model is estimated by

$$c = \hat{\alpha}_0 / \hat{\alpha} = 18.0 / 1.95 = 9.23.$$

The Equation (11) was estimated by the linear least square fitting from the data $(\ln S_i, \ln \hat{\beta}_i)$ given in Table 4 and the resulting equation is

$$\ln \hat{\beta}_i = -17.33 \ln S_i + 114.985 \tag{17}$$

and from this equation the constants b and K are obtained:

$$b = 17.33 \text{ and } K = e^{-114.985} = 1.155 \times 10^{-50}.$$

The critical value $\ell^*_{0.05} = 0.836$ was obtained from Table 2 (for $m = 5$ and $n = 5$) and the S-N curve relations for $N_i = \hat{\beta}_i$ and $N_i = X_{Ai}$ are obtained from Equations (12) and (14) as follows:

$$\ln \hat{\beta}_i = -17.33 \ln S_i + 114.555 \tag{18}$$

and

$$\ln X_{Ai} = -17.33 \ln S_i + 112.195 \tag{19}$$

The estimates $\hat{\beta}_i$ and the relations (17), (18) and (19) are graphed in Figure 1 with experimental points denoted by open circles.

Figure 1. S-N Curve for T300/5208 Graphite/Epoxy $[0/90/+45]_s$.

The residual strength degradation model is examined for the same Composite material T300/5208 G/E [0/90/+45]_s.

Nine replicas of specimens after undertaking 10,000 fatigue cycles at the stress level 414 MPa were experimentally tested for residual strength and their values are given in Table 5.

TABLE 5
RESIDUAL STRENGTH DATA G/E [0/90/+45]_s

After n=10,000 Fatigue Cycles at S = 414 MPa

466.0	563.5	581.2
522.5	563.7	585.9
554.3	568.4	606.3

The validation of the residual strength degradation model was examined by comparing Equation (7) and the residual strength data given in Table 5, which was shown in Figure 2. The data fits Equation (8) reasonably well. This can be seen statistically by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov goodness of fit test since the K-S statistic is .216 and the critical value is .271 for the significance level .05.

Figure 2. Residual Strength, MPa.

REFERENCES

1. Hahn, H. T. and Kim, R. Y., "Fatigue Behavior of Composite Laminate", J. Composite Materials, Vol. 10, 1976, pp. 156-180.
2. Yang, J. N. and Liu, M. D., "Residual Strength Degradation Model and Theory of Periodic Proof Tests for Graphite/Epoxy Laminates", J. Composite Materials, Vol. 11, 1977, pp. 177-203.
3. Thoman, D. R., Bain, L. J. and Antle, C. E., "Inferences on the Parameters of Weibull Distribution", Technometrics, Vol. 11, 1969, pp. 445-460.
4. Cohen, A. C., "Maximum likelihood estimation in the Weibull distribution based on complete and censored samples", Technometrics, Vol. 7, 1965, pp. 579-588.
5. Park, W. J., "Pooled Estimate of the Parameters on Weibull Distributions", Technical Report AFML-TR-79-4112, Air Force Materials Laboratory, 1979.
6. Lemon, G. H. and Wattier, J. B., "Confidence and 'A' and 'B' Allowable Factors for Weibull Distribution", IEEE Trans on Reliability, Vol. R-25, 1976, pp. 16-19.
7. Gibbons, J. D., "Non-parametric Statistical Inference", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1971.